

CHALLENGES IN PROTECTING INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS DURING DATA SHARING

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Annotation

This thesis investigates the problems arising in the context of intellectual rights protection during data sharing. While data sharing offers significant benefits such as accelerating innovation and enhancing product and service quality, it also introduces complex legal and ethical challenges, particularly concerning intellectual property rights. The research categorizes these challenges into three main areas: conflicts over copyright, patent infringements, and trade secret violations. Through a detailed analysis, the thesis explores specific cases where these issues manifest, including unauthorized use of copyrighted materials, unlicensed use of patented technologies, and improper disclosure of trade secrets. The study emphasizes the importance of understanding these conflicts to develop effective legal and strategic frameworks for their resolution. Additionally, it examines various conflict resolution methods, both formal and informal, and their implications for maintaining sustainable business relationships. The findings aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of the intellectual rights issues in data sharing and offer practical solutions for mitigating these challenges.

Keywords:

Data sharing, intellectual rights, intellectual property, information exchange, intellectual property disputes, data sharing problems, copyright, trade secrets, patent conflicts.

Data sharing can accelerate innovation processes, improve the quality of products and services, and facilitate research and development. This practice is a domain-independent process that involves granting third parties access to one's databases. These third parties can include other companies, individuals, or government institutions. Aggregated data is often utilized to develop new applications and services. The purposes for which data can be used and how they are presented are determined within the framework of legal agreements between data providers, government consumers, and other stakeholders (*Jussen and others, 2023*), depending on the specific use case.

Each forms of data sharing process presents unique challenges and opportunities, requiring tailored approaches to ensure secure, efficient exchange of data. However, despite these clear advantages, intellectual property disputes frequently arise during the data-sharing process.

Intellectual property rights, including copyrights, patents, trademarks, and trade secrets, are crucial for protecting creativity and innovation. In a data-sharing environment, conflicts related to these rights can emerge, posing both legal and ethical dilemmas. Understanding the nature and causes of these conflicts is essential for developing effective strategies for their resolution and prevention.

Possible problems related to the topic can be categorised as follows:

a) Conflicts between parties regarding the violation of intellectual rights in the practice of information exchange: in this case, during participation in general joint research projects, one party appropriates unpublished or unpatented information or invention belonging to the second party, to third parties share or publish;

b) In the process of exchanging information, one of the users includes copyrighted, patented or confidential information for mutual use;

c) Copyright infringement of the platform or software on which the data sharing process is carried out.

It can be said that the category *A* mainly involves following issues:

1. Copyright conflicts;
2. Patent disputes;
3. Trademark conflicts
4. Leakage of trade secrets

One of the most common disputes in the data-sharing process is copyright infringement. For example, sharing scientific articles, software, or multimedia materials may raise questions about the legality of using and distributing these works. As *Pr. I. Rustambekov (2016)* notes, nowadays the majority of offenses on the Internet are directly related to copyright infringement when the distribution of works without the permission of copyright holders. This type of infringement occurs when one of the participants uses copyrighted information without the proper permission of the copyright owner. Copyright protects original works in literature, music, art, and other fields, giving authors the exclusive right to use and distribute their works.

Another prevalent issue is patent infringement, which occurs when information containing patented technologies or methods is used or distributed

without the permission of the patent owner. Patents grant exclusive rights to use, manufacture, and sell inventions, thereby protecting innovative technical solutions in various fields. Illegal use of such technologies can have serious legal and financial consequences for violators. Examples of patent infringement include manufacturing and selling products containing patented components or technology without obtaining a license from the patent owner, using patented methods or processes in production, research, or other commercial activities without the permission of the patent owner, providing services involving the use of patented technologies without an appropriate license, distributing information containing patented elements, and publishing or transmitting technical documents, drawings, or data containing patented elements without the permission of the patent holder. In addition, software containing proprietary methods without complying with the terms of the license or posting other materials in the public domain can also constitute patent infringement.

Also, a trade secret violation occurs when confidential information protected as a trade secret is disclosed or used without proper authorization. A trade secret includes any information of economic importance, unknown to third parties and protected by measures aimed at ensuring its confidentiality. Illegal use of such information can seriously harm the company or the person who has the information. Trade secrets (*Carroll, 2015*) can be breached when sharing information between companies or project teams. This occurs when confidential information provided by one party to another for use in a project is disclosed or misused without proper authorization. Trade secrets include confidential business plans, technical drawings, customer and supplier information, and other commercially valuable information.

Conflict resolution is an important aspect of business and project management, especially in complex and multi-layered business relationships. Disputes can arise for a variety of reasons, including disputes over contractual obligations, infringement of intellectual property rights, or as *Kirsanov(2022)* states: conflicts of interest and other issues. Effective and timely resolution of such disputes is important for maintaining business relations, minimizing financial and reputational losses, and ensuring sustainable business development. There are different methods and ways of resolving disputes that can be adapted according to the specific situation and the needs of the parties. These methods include both formal legal procedures and informal alternative approaches. It should be noted that choosing the right method of dispute

resolution can have a significant impact on the outcome of the case and the future of the relationship between the parties.

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